

BARRIERS TO REPORT THE OCCUPATIONAL TO EXPOSURE THE NEEDLE STICK INJURIES AT PEOPLE MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL NAWABSHAH

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Abstract

Background: Needle stick and sharp injuries (NSSIs) are recognized as one of the most frequent occupational dangers among nurses and paramedics globally. These injuries put healthcare workers at risk for blood-borne infections like HIV, Hepatitis B, and Hepatitis C, which can be lethal. Even though most healthcare facilities have post-exposure prophylaxis and reporting mechanisms in place, underreporting is still a problem. Failing to report such instances not only delays critical medical care but also undermines institutional infection control efforts and makes it more difficult to implement effective preventive measures.

Methodology: This study was a descriptive cross-sectional, a stratified random sampling technique was used and conducted from September to November 2025 at People Medical College hospital Nawabshah, sample size of this study was 417.

Result: Overall incidence of needle stick injuries was (72.6%) among healthcare workers. The reported their participant's clear and simple reporting methods used (30.9%). The large group reported was training and awareness method used in future (51.1%). Nurses experienced a higher number of injuries (45.3%) compared to other healthcare staff. The most common device causing injury was the hollow-bore needle (42.9%).

Conclusion: This study concluded barriers of needle stick injuries among health care workers at PMCH Nawabshah were alarmingly high. Addressing barriers is crucial to minimize needle stick injuries and enhance overall clinical practice.

INTRODUCTION

Health care workers are particularly prone to injuries from contaminated sharp objects such as needles. These injuries can lead to serious such as HIV, HBV, HCV and Treponema(1). Accidents were more likely to occur in these workplaces due to factors such as understaffing, a work culture that plays down

standard safety procedures, or perhaps previous training (2). According to the national institute of occupational safety and health (NIOSH) in the United States, intravenous devices, hypodermics needles, blood collection needles, and needles for IV administration systems are regarded as the leading

sources of cases for needles stick injuries. Injuries from sharps contaminated with pathogens results in the significant increased risk of infection(3). The underreporting of injuries tend to result from various factors such as forgetting to report the incident, of the risk associated with needle stick injuries, fear of confessing the misuse of equipment for causing the injury, and being too preoccupied (4). A number of studies have elaborated on the risk of factors and made suggestions for preventive measures(5). The prevalence of NSIs in Bangladesh varies widely, with reported frequencies ranging from 30% to 73%. Bangladesh's healthcare system faces numerous challenges that increase the risk of needle stick injuries(6). The prevalence of NSIs in Bangladesh varies widely, with reported frequencies ranging from 30% to 73%. Bangladesh's healthcare system faces numerous challenges that increase the risk of needle stick injuries(6). Heating needles, poor techniques when performing high risk procedures (7). The probability of infection transmission through a needle stick injury is approximately 3–10% for hepatitis B, 3% for hepatitis C, and 0.3% for HIV. On average, healthcare workers face four NSIs each year, with contributing factors including inadequate supplies, excessive reliance on injections, poor access to sharps containers, staffing shortages, needle recapping, and insufficient adoption of safer needle technologies. Transmission of at least twenty different pathogens by injuries due to sharps instruments and needle- sticks has been reported in the literature(8). A more significant decrease was determined by the introduction of safety-engineered devices (SED), which integrate a mechanism for needle stick prevention, and therefore, reduce the exposure by modifying or isolating the hazard(9, 10). WHO stated that hospital environment is the common place for NSIs among HCWs and reported evidence of Hepatitis B (37.6%), Hepatitis C (39%) and HIV syndrome (4.4%) are the result of such deleterious NSI(11,12). Barriers to reporting include Fear of blame or punishment, thinking the injury is 'not serious', no proper follow-up or support from the hospital(13, 14). Ghanei Gheshlagh et al.'s study showed the prevalence of needle head injury among healthcare personnel in Iran is 42.5%, and this rate is higher in females than males (47 vs. 42%). NSI-related risk factors have not yet been properly

identified in Iran(15). Nurses face high NSI risk due to their frontline role in patient care, yet limited Indian studies assess their knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) on this issue(16, 17). The risk of transmission of blood borne pathogens with their level of endemically within the catchment area(18,19). These facilities need to be compelled to systematic manner the rate of such injuries their employees yearly. Besides the health risk they present physically, needle-stick injuries can also cause serious emotional and psychological stress on health care workers (20). Bangladesh's healthcare system faces numerous challenges that increase the risk of needle stick injuries. Limited resources, overcrowded facilities, and a lack of comprehensive training on occupational hazards contribute to the prevalence of these injuries.(21).

Aim of Study:

The aim of this study is to determine how common needle stick and sharp injuries are among healthcare workers at People's Medical College Hospitals and to explore the barriers they face in reporting these injuries.

Objective of Study:

1. To assess the barriers of Needle Stick Injuries among healthcare workers People's Medical College Hospitals.

Material & Methods:

This was descriptive cross-sectional study, which is conducted from November 2025 to January 2026 at People Medical College Hospital Nawabshah. A stratified random sampling technique was used. The sample size for this study was calculated using the standard statistical formula for prevalence studies, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. Based on previously reported prevalence rates of needle stick and sharp injuries among healthcare workers (HCWs) in Pakistan, the estimated prevalence was taken as 48%. Considering a total population of approximately 20,000 HCWs, the needed sample size was calculated to be around 375 participants. To account for an anticipated 10% non-response rate, a total of 417 participants will be approached to ensure at least 375 valid responses for analysis.

Inclusion Criteria

This study was including doctors, nurses, and paramedics working at People’s Medical College Hospital, Nawabshah, who have been employed there for at least six months. Healthcare workers who have experienced a needle stick or sharp injury while carrying out their professional duties will be invited to participate. Participation in the study will be completely voluntary, and only those who willingly agree and provide informed consent will be included.

Exclusion Criteria

Administrative or non-clinical staff (clerks, cleaners, managers). Anyone who refuses to give consent.

Tools for Data Collection:

Tables and figures were used to display demographic data (age, gender, profession, and years of service). The Chi-square test and Kendall's test were used in History of injuries (whether they experienced NSI/Sharps injuries, how often, where, and how). The Chi-square test and Kendall's test were also employed for data analysis in the reporting practices (whether they reported or not, reasons for not reporting). The chi-square test and kendell’s test were used in Barriers to reporting (personal, organizational, systemic).

Result:

Table no 01: Demographic Information

S:no	item	Frequency (percentage)
1	Distribution of age of subject Up to 30 year 31-45 years 45-60 years	245 (58.8%) 152(36.5%) 20(4.8%)
2	Distribution of Gender of subject Male Female	202(48.4%) 215(51.6%)
3	Distribution of profession of subject Doctors Nurses Paramedics	151(36.2%) 189(45.3%) 77(18.5%)
4	Distribution of Experience of subject Maximum Minimum Std. Deviation	30.00 .00 5.02866
5	Distribution of Department of subject Emergency Surgery Medicine ICU Other	66(16.5%) 139(33.3%) 97(23.3%) 53(12.7%) 59(14.1%)

Table no 01: showed demographic data of the study participant. Age of subject was observed up to 30 years were 245(58.7) %, 31 to 45 Years were 152 (36.4) %, and 45 to 60 years were 20 (4.7) %. In

terms gender study in included (48.4) % males responses, and (51.6) % females responses. In this study, Doctors were 151 (36.2) % Nurses were 189 (45.3) %, and Paramedics were 77 (18.4) %. In

addition the maximum value is 30.00, minimum value is .00, and std. deviation value is 5.02866. In this study, 69 (16.5)% emergency ward response were, 139 (33.3)% surgery ward response were,

97(23.3)% medicine ward response were, 53 (12.7)% ICU ward response were, 59 (14.1)% other wards response.

Table No: 02 Distribution of table Age to compare with Reporting Practices and Barriers

S no:	Item	Frequency (Percentage %)	P value
1	Have you experienced needle stick or sharp injury Yes No	303 (72.6%) 114 (27.3%)	.004
2	How many times last 12 months Once 2-3times More 3 times	174 (41.7%) 177 (42.4%) 66 (15.8%)	.007
3	Device caused the injury Hollow-bore Scalpel Suture needle other	179 (42.9%) 62 (14.8%) 130 (31.1%) 46 (11%)	.001
4	Report your most recent injury Yes No	240 (57.5%) 177 (42.4%)	.000
5	If no, what was reason any one tick. Injury minor Needle unused Did not reporting procedure No time because workload Fear of stigma Nothing after previous reports Other	126 (30.2%) 106 (25.4%) 48 (11.5%) 34 (9.1%) 53 (12.7%) 36 (8.6%) 14 (3.3%)	.009
6	If yes, how did you report it Written form Inform verbally Online system Other	84(20.1%) 281 (67.3%) 15 (3.5%) 37 (8.8%)	.069
7	What improvement would make easier for you to report in the future? Clear and simple reporting system Training and awareness Confidentiality Institutional support Other	129 (30.9%) 216 (51.7%) 48 (11.5%) 14 (3.3%) 10 (2.3%)	.012

Table no 02: that shows the majority of the participants, 303 (72.6) % reported having experienced a needle stick injury and of participants, 114 (27.3) % reported having no experienced. In research highly significant association between ($p = .004$). Among those injured in the last 12 months, those injured once 174 (41.7) %. The largest group reported an injury 2-3 times 177(42.4) %. A smaller portion 66 (15.8) % reported more than three times injuries in the same period. This value is also highly significant ($p= .007$). The most common device causing injury was the hollow- bore needle 179 (42.9) %, the scalpel 62 (14.8) % was the causing injury, further suture needle 130 (31.1) % causing injury and other 46 (11.0) % reported causing device. This is not significant value ($p=.184$). That shows the reported experiencing a recent injury participants 240 (57.5%) reported experiencing an injury. The compare to participants 177 (42.4%) reporting no experience with injury. This was found to be highly significantly ($p=.000$). That shows the main reason was the belief of the injury as minor injury 126 (30.2%). The other reasons included the belief that

the needle had not needle unused 106 (25.4%). Because did not know how to the reporting procedure 48 (11.5%), because of the workload participants 34 (9.1%), to avoid the fear of stigma 53(12.7%), since nothing happen after pervious injury reports 36 (8.6%), and 14 (3.3%) other reasons. This is also not significant value ($p= .421$). Among those reported their injury, the majority used verbally methods informing 281 (67.3%). A significantly smaller group used written forms 84 (20.1%), other methods 37 (8.8%), and online methods 15 (3.5%). It was not statistically significant ($p=.411$). That shows the reported their participant's clear and simple reporting methods used 129 (30.9%), because the large group reported was training and awareness method used in future 216 (51.1%), and confidentially methods used to reported participants 48 (11.5%), institutional support 14 (3.3%) respectively reported, and other methods used to 10 (2.3%) can health care prodder used this methods. The result was not statistically significant ($p=.012$).

Table No: 03 Distribution of table gender compare with Reporting Practices and Barriers

S no:	Item	Frequency (Percentage %)	P value
1	Have you experienced needle stick or sharp injury Yes No	303 (72.6%) 114 (27.3%)	.001
2	How many times last 12 months Once 2-3times More 3 times	174 (41.7%) 177 (42.4%) 66 (15.8%)	.002
3	Device caused the injury Hollow-bore Scalpel Suture needle other	179 (42.9%) 62 (14.8%) 130 (31.1%) 46 (11%)	.003
4	Report your most recent injury Yes No	240 (57.5%) 177 (42.4%)	.006
5	If no, what was reason any one tick. Injury minor Needle unused Did not reporting procedure	126 (30.2%) 106 (25.4%) 48 (11.5%)	.009

	No time because workload Fear of stigma Nothing after previous reports Other	34 (9.1%) 53 (12.7%) 36 (8.6%) 14 (3.3%)	
6	If yes, how did you report it Written form Inform verbally Online system Other	84(20.1%) 281 (67.3%) 15 (3.5%) 37 (8.8%)	.008
7	What improvement would make easier for you to report in the future? Clear and simple reporting system Training and awareness Confidentiality Institutional support Other	129 (30.9%) 216 (51.7%) 48 (11.5%) 14 (3.3%) 10 (2.3%)	.005

Table no 03: that shows the significant majority of the participants, 303 (72.6) % reported having experienced a needle stick injury and minority of participants, 114 (27.3) % reported having no experienced. In research not significant association between ($p=.171$). Among those injured in the last 12 months, those injured once 174 (41.7) %. The largest group reported an injury 2-3 times 177(42.4) %. A smaller portion 66 (15.8) % reported more than three times injuries in the same period. This value is also highly significant ($p= .002$). The most common device causing injury was the hollow- bore needle 179 (42.9) %, the scalpel 62 (14.8) % was the causing injury, further suture needle 130 (31.1) % causing injury and other 46 (11.0) % reported causing device. This is not significant value ($p=.109$). That shows the reported experiencing a recent injury participants 240 (57.5%) reported experiencing an injury. The compare to participants 177 (42.4%) reporting no experience with injury. This was found to be significantly ($p=.006$). That shows the main reason was the belief of the injury as minor injury

126 (30.2%). The other reasons included the belief that the needle had not needed unused 106 (25.6%). Because did not know how to the reporting procedure 48 (11.5%), because of the workload participants 34 (8.1%), to avoid the fear of stigma 53(12.7%), since nothing happen after pervious injury reports 36 (8.6%), and 14 (3.3%) other reasons. This is also significant value ($p= .009$). That show the participants was written form used 84 (20.1%), the majority used for verbally forms methods 281 (67.3%), online system method used for 15 (3.5%) and other methods used 37 (8.8%). This is not significant value is ($p=.411$). That shows the reported their participant's clear and simple reporting methods used 129 (30.9%), because the large group reported was training and awareness method used in future 216 (51.7%), and confidentially methods used to reported participants 48 (11.5%), institutional support 14 (3.3%) respectively reported, and other methods used to 10 (2.3%) can health care prodder used this methods. The result was statistically significant ($p=.005$).

Table No: 04 Distribution of table Profession compare with Reporting Practices and Barriers

S no:	Item	Frequency (Percentage %)	P value
1	Have you experienced needle stick or sharp injury Yes	303 (72.6%)	.003

	No	114 (27.3%)	
2	How many times last 12 months Once 2-3times More 3 times	174 (41.7%) 177 (42.4%) 66 (15.8%)	.000
3	Device caused the injury Hollow-bore Scalpel Suture needle other	179 (42.9%) 62 (14.8%) 130 (31.1%) 46 (11%)	.002
4	Report your most recent injury Yes No	240 (57.5%) 177 (42.4%)	.000
5	If no, what was reason any one tick. Injury minor Needle unused Did not reporting procedure No time because workload Fear of stigma Nothing after previous reports Other	126 (30.2%) 106 (25.4%) 48 (11.5%) 34 (9.1%) 53 (12.7%) 36 (8.6%) 14 (3.3%)	.005
6	If yes, how did you report it Written form Inform verbally Online system Other	84(20.1%) 281 (67.3%) 15 (3.5%) 37 (8.8%)	.008
7	What improvement would make easier for you to report in the future? Clear and simple reporting system Training and awareness Confidentiality Institutional support Other	129 (30.9%) 216 (51.7%) 48 (11.5%) 14 (3.3%) 10 (2.3%)	.001

Table no 04: That shows the significant majority of the participants, 303 (72.6) % reported having experienced a needle stick injury and minority of participants, 114 (27.3) % reported having no experienced. This is significant association between ($p=.003$). Among those injured in the last 12 months, those injured once 174 (41.7) %. The largest group reported an injury 2-3 times 177(42.4) %. A smaller portion 66 (15.8) % reported more than three times injuries in the same period. This

value is also highly significant ($p= .000$). The most common device causing injury was the hollow- bore needle 179 (42.9) %, the scalpel 62 (14.8) % was the causing injury, further suture needle 130 (31.1) % causing injury and other 46 (11.0) % reported causing device. This is significant value ($p=.002$). That shows the reported experiencing a recent injury participants 240 (57.5%) reported experiencing an injury. The compare to participants 177 (42.4%) reporting no experience with injury. This was found to be highly significantly ($p=.000$).That shows the

main reason was the belief of the injury as minor injury 126 (30.2%). The other reasons included the belief that the needle had not needed unused 106 (25.4%). Because did not know how to the reporting procedure 48 (11.5%), because of the workload participants 34 (8.1%), to avoid the fear of stigma 53(12.7%), since nothing happen after pervious injury reports 36 (8.6%), and 14 (3.3%) other reasons. This is also no significant value ($p= .293$). That show the participants was written form used 84 (20.1%), the majority used for verbally forms methods 281 (67.3%), online system method used for 15 (3.5%) and other methods used 37 (8.8%).

This is not significant value is ($p=.559$). That shows the reported their participant's clear and simple reporting methods used 129 (30.9%), because the large group reported was training and awareness method used in future 216 (51.7%), and confidentially methods used to reported participants 48 (11.5%), institutional support 14 (3.3%) respectively reported, and other methods used to 10 (2.3%) can health care prodder used this methods. The result was not statistically significant ($p=.176$).

Table No: 05 Distribution of table Experience compare with Reporting Practices and Barriers

S no:	Item	Frequency (Percentage %)	P value
1	Have you experienced needle stick or sharp injury Yes No	303 (72.6%) 114 (27.3%)	.001
2	How many times last 12 months Once 2-3times More 3 times	174 (41.7%) 177 (42.4%) 66 (15.8%)	.000
3	Device caused the injury Hollow-bore Scalpel Suture needle other	179 (42.9%) 62 (14.8%) 130 (31.1%) 46 (11%)	.005
4	Report your most recent injury Yes No	240 (57.5%) 177 (42.4%)	.000
5	If no, what was reason any one tick. Injury minor Needle unused Did not reporting procedure No time because workload Fear of stigma Nothing after previous reports Other	126 (30.2%) 106 (25.4%) 48 (11.5%) 34 (9.1%) 53 (12.7%) 36 (8.6%) 14 (3.3%)	.003
6	If yes, how did you report it Written form Inform verbally Online system Other	84(20.1%) 281 (67.3%) 15 (3.5%) 37 (8.8%)	.005

7	What improvement would make easier for you to report in the future? Clear and simple reporting system Training and awareness Confidentiality Institutional support Other	129 (30.9%) 216 (51.7%) 48 (11.5%) 14 (3.3%) 10 (2.3%)	.000
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Table no: 05 that shows the significant majority of the participants, 303 (72.6) % reported having experienced a needle stick injury and minority of participants, 114 (27.3) % reported having no experienced. In research highly significant association between ($p=.001$). Among those injured in the last 12 months, those injured once 174 (41.7) %. The largest group reported an injury 2-3 times 177(42.4) %. A smaller portion 66 (15.8) % reported more than three times injuries in the same period. This value is also highly significant ($p= .000$). The most common device causing injury was the hollow-bore needle 179 (42.9) %, the scalpel 62 (14.8) % was the causing injury, further suture needle 130 (31.1) % causing injury and other 46 (11.0) % reported causing device. This is not significant value ($p=.489$). That shows the reported experiencing a recent injury participants 240 (57.5%) reported experiencing an injury. The compare to participants 177 (42.4%) reporting no experience with injury. This was found to be highly significantly ($p=.000$). That shows the main reason was the belief of the injury as minor injury 126 (30.2%). The other reasons included the

belief that the needle had not needle unused 106 (25.4%). Because did not know how to the reporting procedure 48 (11.5%), because of the workload participants 34 (9.1%), to avoid the fear of stigma 53(12.7%), since nothing happen after pervious injury reports 36 (8.6%), and 14 (3.3%) other reasons. This is also not significant value ($p= .550$). Among those reported their injury, the majority used verbally methods informing 281 (67.3%). A significantly smaller group used written forms 84 (20.1%), other methods 37 (8.8%), and online methods 15 (3.5%). It was not statistically significant ($p=.074$). That shows the reported their participant's clear and simple reporting methods used 129 (30.9%), because the large group reported was training and awareness method used in future 216 (51.7%), and confidentially methods used to reported participants 48 (11.5%), institutional support 14 (3.3%) respectively reported, and other methods used to 10 (2.3%) can health care prodder used this methods. The result was statistically significant ($p=.000$).

Table No: 06 Distribution of table Department compare with Reporting Practices and Barriers

S no:	Item	Frequency (Percentage %)	P value
1	Have you experienced needle stick or sharp injury Yes No	303 (72.6%) 114 (27.3%)	.035
2	How many times last 12 months Once 2-3times More 3 times	174 (41.7%) 177 (42.4%) 66 (15.8%)	.007
3	Device caused the injury Hollow-bore Scalpel	179 (42.9%) 62 (14.8%)	.009

	Suture needle other	130 (31.1%) 46 (11%)	
4	Report your most recent injury Yes No	240 (57.5%) 177 (42.4%)	.001
5	If no, what was reason any one tick. Injury minor Needle unused Did not reporting procedure No time because workload Fear of stigma Nothing after previous reports Other	126 (30.2%) 106 (25.4%) 48 (11.5%) 34 (9.1%) 53 (12.7%) 36 (8.6%) 14 (3.3%)	
6	If yes, how did you report it Written form Inform verbally Online system Other	84(20.1%) 281 (67.3%) 15 (3.5%) 37 (8.8%)	.007
7	What improvement would make easier for you to report in the future? Clear and simple reporting system Training and awareness Confidentiality Institutional support Other	129 (30.9%) 216 (51.7%) 48 (11.5%) 14 (3.3%) 10 (2.3%)	.515

Table no: 06 that shows the significant majority of the participants, 303 (72.6) % reported having experienced a needle stick injury and minority of participants, 114 (27.3) % reported having no experienced. In research highly significant association between ($p=.000$). Among those injured in the last 12 months, those injured once 174 (41.7) %. The largest group reported an injury 2-3 times 177(42.4) %. A smaller portion 66 (15.8) % reported more than three times injuries in the same period. This value is also not significant ($p= .530$). The most common device causing injury was the hollow- bore needle 179 (42.9) %, the scalpel 62 (14.8) % was the causing injury, further suture needle 130 (31.1) % causing injury and other 46 (11.0) % reported causing device. This is not significant value ($p=.317$). That shows the reported experiencing a recent injury participants 240 (57.5%) reported experiencing an injury. The compare to participants 177 (42.4%)

reporting no experience with injury. This was found to be highly significantly ($p=.000$). That shows the main reason was the belief of the injury as minor injury 126 (30.2%). The other reasons included the belief that the needle had not needle unused 106 (25.4%). Because did not know how to the reporting procedure 48 (11.5%), because of the workload participants 34 (8.1%), to avoid the fear of stigma 53(12.7%), since nothing happen after pervious injury reports 36 (8.6%), and 14 (3.3%) other reasons. This is also not significant value ($p= .547$). Among those reported their injury, the majority used verbally methods informing 281 (67.3%). A significantly smaller group used written forms 84 (20.1%), other methods 37 (8.8%), and online methods 15 (3.5%). It was statistically significant ($p=.007$). That shows the reported their participant's clear and simple reporting methods used 129 (30.9%), because the large group reported was

training and awareness method used in future 216 (51.7%), and confidentially methods used to reported participants 48 (11.5%), institutional support 14 (3.3%) respectively reported, and other methods used to 10 (2.3%) can health care prodder used this methods. The result was not statistically significant ($p=.515$).

Discussion:

This study was a descriptive cross-sectional study, in which a stratified random sampling technique was used, the aim of this study is to find out the barriers healthcare workers face in reporting NSSIs and to measure how common these injuries are among staff at People's Medical College Hospital Nawabshah was overall incidence of needle stick injuries was (72.6%) among healthcare workers. Furthermore, IN my study, employees who were 30 years of age or younger reported the highest incidents (58.8%), while those who were older reported fewer incidents. Both studies generally show that as healthcare workers age, their risk of needle stick injuries decreases. Similarly According to previous study, needle stick injuries are more common in younger age groups, such as those between the ages of 21 and 23, with very few occurrences in older age groups (22). A total of 417 healthcare workers with needle stick injuries were examined in my study. There were (51.56%) females and (48.44%) males among them, including a higher percentage of females. On the other hand, a previous study of 2763 workers found that (71.4%) of them were males and (28.6%) were females. The greater participates of female healthcare professionals especially nurses, in direct patient care and needle related procedures in the current study may account for this discrepancy and raise their risk of needle stick injuries (8). In my study found a higher rate of repeated exposures over the last 12 months, only (41.7%) of employees reported a single exposure. Meanwhile (42.4%) experienced needle stick injuries two to three times, and (15.8%) reported exposure more than three times this is statistically significant ($p=.007$). In the previous study, most healthcare workers reported experiencing a needle stick injury only once with (87%) including this. A smaller healthcare (13%) reported being exposed two or more times (23). In my study work experience of participants was 5.02 ± 5.03 years, with

a maximum of 30 years and a minimum of 0 years. It can be seen that the workforce was in the beginning of their career, and with a lack of expertise, the risk of injury from needle stick may be higher. The most common group the healthcare workers with needle stick injuries in the previous study were healthcare workers who had experience from 1 to 10 years (66.23%), and the next group was healthcare workers who had experienced ranging from 11 to 20 years (21.19%). those with experience ranging from 21 to 30 years (7.28%) and above 30 years (5.30%) had fewer injuries (24). In my study continues to represent the highest professional group to be nurses, and slightly lower at (45.3%) however, the representation of physicians has increased to (36.2%), and the paramedics represent (18.5%). In my study thus reveals a relatively higher representation of physicians and a clearer representation of paramedics compare to the previous study, through the dominant presence of nurses continues to remain the same. It appears that both studies reveal the highest professional representation to be nurses. The previous study revealed the composition to be (50%) nurses, (27%) physicians, and (23%) others. Amongst physicians, (45%) were residents and interns, and (55%) were senior's physicians (22). The same pattern has been noted in the current investigation. The surgery department accounted for (33.3%) of all injuries, followed by the medicine department (23.3%) and the emergency department (16.5%) injuries occurred in other departments as well as intensive care unit (12.7%). In the previous study, there was a strong correlation between needle stick injuries and the department of work. Surgery, emergency, internal medicine, and pediatrics all had higher injury rates. The remaining departments the number of injuries was lower. This suggests that departments that carry out numerous procedures have a higher risk of needle stick injuries (22). In my study, respondents were asked which aspects would help make future reporting easier. More than half of the participants identify training and awareness (51.7%) as very important, followed by a simple reporting system (30.9%). They were followed by those who identified confidentially (11.5%), support from the institution (3.3%), and other reason (2.3%). This is not statistically significant ($p=.012$). The key reason for

underreporting needle stick and sharp injury in the previous study is a belief that the needle is clean or has not been used, (47.7%) of respondents this reason. There is a positive attitude of respondents toward prevention since (92%) of them were willing to attend training about needle stick injury. The result implies that lack of awareness rather than lack of interest might be a key reason for lack of reporting of needle stick injury (25). In my current study, I found improvements in the reporting of needle stick injuries. Of the 417 total participants in the current study, 240 (57.5%) of the healthcare workers reported, and 177 (42.4%) was not needle stick injury. In the current study, there was a statistically significant difference between those reporting and those not reporting needle stick injuries based on the ($p=.000$). The results from my current study indicate that the reporting rates are higher than those in the previous study, indicating improved awareness and use of reporting procedures regarding needle stick injuries, but that the underreporting of needle stick injuries continues and efforts should be made to improve timely reporting. Out of a total of 144 healthcare professionals involved in the last study, only (38%) reported that they were participants of a needle stick injury, this represents a needle stick injury reporting rate of (73.61%). The discrepancy between what was reported and actual injuries indicates that needle stick injuries are being grossly underreported in the previous study (26). Similar reasons were identified for the current study. The most reported reasons for not reporting were that the injury was not considered serious enough (30.2%), followed by feeling that the syringe had never been used (25.4%). Fear of stigma and lack of time because of workload were other reasons at (12.7%) and (8.1%), respectively. Respondents also mentioned that they did not report because nothing happened following their previous reports. There was no statistical significance ($p=.547$). In a previous study, fear of stigma and discrimination was a highly cited reason for reporting needle stick injuries, where participants tended to strongly agree with this reason, mean score (4.23%). Also, lack of time was a highly cited reason, where participants agreed that heavy workload is a reason for underreporting injuries, mean score (4.31%) (3). The reporting rates were slightly improved but limited in this study as well.

Only 84 (20.1%) write down their injury report, while about 281 (67.3%) did it verbally. Only 15 (3.5%) made use of a reporting form, but 37 (8.8%) made their reports through other methods. No significant difference in reporting methods was identified ($p=.069$). A significant number of healthcare professionals did not formally report needle stick injuries in the previous research. A total of 68 cases revealed that 49 or (77.4%) did not write any reports, only 16 or (20.1%) wrote one report, while 3 or (2.5%) told their clinical instructor. Clearly, there is little formal reporting method used (27). Relative to (27.3%) of not reporting in the current study, a considerable number of respondents (72.6%) have had a needle stick injury, skin puncture, or a sharp object. The difference is statistically significant ($p=.004$). In the previous study, (59.9%) of respondents indicated that they previously received information regarding needle stick injuries, whereas (40.5%) of them indicated that they did not (27). The same trend was identified in my study. The highest percentage of injuries was due to hollow bore needles (42.9%), followed by scalpels (14.8%), and suture needles (31.1%). Fewer injuries were due to other devices. There were no significant differences in these devices ($p=.184$). In the previous study, syringes were responsible for (62.77%) of needle stick injuries, followed by suture needles (23.94%) and scalpels (10.64%). The percentage of injuries caused by scissors and other sharps was least. It is clear that the main source of injury in the previous study was syringes (26).

Conclusion:

Needle stick and sharp injuries are a significant occupational hazard for healthcare workers, with underreporting being a major concern. Addressing these barriers and implementing effective prevention strategies, such as safety protocols, is crucial to reducing the risk of NSSIs.

Recommendation:

This was a descriptive cross-sectional study, conducted only in a People's Medical College Hospital, Nawabshah, limited time, so there is a need to conduct a longitudinal study to determine and provide regular training on needle stick injury prevention, reporting, and management. Raise awareness about needle stick

injury risks and consequence. Streamline reporting processes, make them accessible, and ensure management.

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